

WELFARE SCHEMES FOR WOMEN IN TAMIL NADU DURING THE RULE OF DRAVIDA MUNNETRA KAZAHAGAM (1967-1975)

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Abstract

The Dravidar Kazhagam, though the successor to the justice party.. Its main aim has been to get social liberty and social justice to the place in general. It takes up the cause of the socially backward, especially those called Sudras. E.V.Ramaswany Naicker who assumed its leadership, was given the name Periyar by the women folk of Madras province in 1938 in recognitions and appreciation of his service to uplift them. He steadfastly refused to convert the party into a political one. Therefore it is necessary to include the DravidaKazhagam in a study of the political parties of Madras. In 1944, at a special conference in Salem, the Justice Party was merged with the Self-Respect Movement andDravidarKazahagam. TheDravidarKazhagam started with a demand for independence Dravida Nadu as its political goal.

Introduction

The DravidaMunnetraKazahagam was Founded in 1949 by C.N. Annadurai after a conflict with E.V. Ramasamy Periyar, founder of the DravidaKazahagam. The DravidaMunnetraKazahagam translated as the “Dravidan Progress Federation” is a breakaway faction of Periyar Party called DravidaKagahagam. The DMK was born as a result differences between Periyar the president of the DravidarKazhagam, and some of his prominent followers. Among them were C.N. Annadurai, V.R. Nedunchezian, M. Karunanidhi, K.Anbazhagan, E.V.K.Sampath, K. Mathiazhagam and Govidnasamy. Annadurai and his followers announced their own party on September 17, 1949 at Robinson Park, Royapuram, Madras.

The Landmark Election of (1967-77)

DMK won 138 seats in the election and as a first thing C.N. Annadurai Anna, and Kalaingar Karunandihi among others got the blessing of Periyar in Tiruchy. On 1967 Anna took oath as the chief minister of Tamil Nadu. He inaugurated the name board “Thamizahaga Arasu Thalamal Seyalagam” (Secretariat) at Chennai Saint Jerorge Fort. He also changes the words “Madras Government” into “Thamizahaga Arasu” and „Satyamev Jayate” into Vaimaye vellum. „In the state emblem of Tamil Nadu. Annadurai took three important decisions in his ministry. First he changed the name of the state from Madras to “Tamil Nadu” Second; he enacted the self-respect marriage law. Third, he passed the Anti-Hindi resolution.

After the death of Annadurai

The founder of DMK, C.N. Annadurai Anna, passed away on 1969. The whole of Tamil Nadu mourned his death. A large number of people took part in the funeral that the funeral procession of C.N. Annadurai Anna became a Guinness Record. Kalaingar Karunanidhi penned a poetic obituary titled “Please Let us Your Heart Anna” In 1969 Kalaginar Karunanidhi was elected to lead the party in the DMK’s mala meeting while minister K.A. Mathiazhagan proposed Kalaginar Karunanidhi name, Minister Sathiyavani Muthu endorsed it.

Emergency of DMK Government Dismissal:

The DMK government was dismissed on January 31 1975 for making a resolution to save democracy. Popular DMK leaders were arrested under MISA. Maintenance of internal security act M.K Stalin was arrested and imprisoned for a year. Achievements of DMK As a regional political party, and by forming Government in Tamil Nadu, the DMK has had some significant achievements. Some of these listed below.

- ⊗ The DMK has initiated all-round development in the villages of Tamil Nadu, by implementing the famous Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee scheme, which ensures employment to the youth in villages of Tamil Nadu.
- ⊗ Impetus has been given to industrial growth in the state, by improving the condition of roads, building four-lane and six-lane roads and constructing bridges across the state.
- ⊗ Various projects, linking up rivers with the state have been implemented. Examples of such project are Cauvery-Gundaru linking project taken up at cost of Rs.198 crores; Tamirabarani Karumeniyaru-Nambiyaru.
- ⊗ A historic food security scheme has been launched in the state, where in Lakhs of Beneficiaries have been given rice at rupees one per kilogram of rice.
- ⊗ Zero interest on agricultural Loans has been implemented, to help

farmers carry on their agricultural activities more comfortably. More than one corner of people has been given free house sites in the state, for construction of a proper shelter with government aid. In protest against Hindi being made the official language, the DMK has successfully introduced Tamil as a compulsory language till 10th standard in all schools in the state of Tamil Nadu.

Welfare Schemes for Women in Tamil Nadu 1969-1977

The state social welfare board was re-constituted in Dumber 1968 with Thirumathi ChampalakhsmiVenkatchalam as chairman. The full board met thrice during the period under report. The members of the new board were allotted specified areas in the state to attend to their work.

Women's Welfare Committees

In order that non-official participation may help the growth of democratic development at district and block levels, women's welfare committees have been formed in all the 13 district and in 359 blocks in the state.

Services Women's Welfare Committees

The total number of Mjukkyasevikas and Gramasvikas in position in 266 and 710 respectively as against the sanctioned strength of 345 Mukhyasevikas and 752 Gramasevikas. There are 48 women's welfare organizations in charge of 48 women's welfare branches in the state centers, the centers at Pammal Chingalpat district conducted at the Azeeznagare, South Arcot district are exclusively. These posts are interchangeable with health Gramasevikas. All these personnel attend to the programmer welfare of women and children in the blocks municipalities and towns in the state under the guidance for the district women's welfare officers. They are also about 500 voluntary workers in braches and it sub-centers to assist the women's welfare organization in their activitie and the help by looking after the branch work when the women's welfare organization go on cleave and till a substitute is posted when they go long leave.

The State Social Welfare Board

The State Social Welfare Board and the Women's Welfare Department continued their status-quo with reference to their integrated role. The fall board meeting of the Tamil Nadu State Social Welfare Board were held on 22nd January 1960, 12th August 1969, 26th October

1969, December 9th and January 1970, when application for grant-in-aid in respect of annual grant, Mahila Mandal grants and holiday camps for 1969-70 and 1970-71 were considered and recommended to the Central Social Welfare Board. Other important Perain meetings. The standing committee of the state social welfare board met on 18th March 1969 1st September 1969, 25th September 1969, 14th October 1969 and 25th March 1970, when important and urgent matters pertaining to cleaning campaign launched by the women's voluntary force and Gandhi centenary celebration were discussed and late application for annual grants and holiday camps were considered.

Mahilamandal

Under Mahila Mandal Grant, the central social welfare board has sanctioned a sum of Rs. 56,835 to 13 Mahila Mandal Institutions up to 31st March 1971 after adjusting the unspent balance of Rs. 1,367 of the previous year. Under urban pilot project a sum of Rs. 30,000 a sum of Rs. 25,61,190 has been released. Under the plan period grant, a sum of Rs. 1,72,329,69 has been released up to March 1971 as against a sum of Rs. 2,16,970 sanctioned to 68 voluntary institutions. Under the annual grant 1970-71 the Central Social Welfare board conveyed approval of sanctions for 144 institutions covering a sum of Rs. 1,70,000. Against this amount a sum of Rs. 1,55,318 has been released. The central of education for adult women to six institutions covering a sum of Rs. 1,60,00 for 1969-71 and to two institutions covering an amount of Rs. 70,000 for 1970-72. The amount actually released were Rs. 6,000 and Rs. 1,11,000 respectively. Eight voluntary institutions have conceded up adult women and send them up for special E.S.L.C examination held in May 1969.

Child welfare

Pre-school programme-CARE feeding was being implemented in 1,000 Preschools. Another feeding programme called the „Balhar Feeding Programme“ was introduced in 710 pre-schools demonstration feeding programme with cent per cent government of India's assistance was also implemented with 80 beneficiaries in each centre. Integrated child welfare demonstration project Poonamallee.1 This project had 50 pre-schools and 10 creches with strength of 40 and 10 children in each respectively. Mid-day meals are supplied to the children.

Working Women's Hostel

The hostel for working women at Emgore, Madras continued to function with the full sanctioned strength of 25 inmates. During 1973-74 a sum of Rs. 35,000 was sanctioned by the government to the guild of service Madras for construction of Working Women's Hostel. The government of India also sanctioned sum of Rs.80,560 to the Madras SevaSadan, Madras for addition to the existing Working Women Hostel.

Women Welfare Programmers

This programmer in to organize of rural areas to come together in Mandrams ensuring across the various social economic barriers. Accordingly MahalirMandrams at the rate of 30 for each panchyats using were established and these continue to function. To encourage MahalirMandrams to undertake different type of economic activities each were given to the best MahalirMandrams. A sum of Rs. 21,200 was sanctioned for 1976-77. In each of 104 selected blocks 6 MahalirMandrams were selected during 1976-77 and nutrition demonstration showing better uses of local food and introducing balanced menus were organized

Special Schemes for Women

A new scheme on payment of annual stipend of Rs.150 for 1,000 poor women in the age group of 16-30 whose family income is less than Rs. 3,000 per annum in order to help them to acquire vacationed training in the form of type writing is also introduced during the year 1977- 78. Further four guidance bureaus at madras city. Coimbatore, Thanjavur and Madurai for helping widowed women to get assistance for obtaining life insurance and provident fund benefits advice on educational and employment opportunities and guidance regarding admission of their children in orphanages, educational institutions are also set up by this department during the year 1977-78. Government have also approved a scheme for the supply of books and note books free of cost to the children of widows whose family income is less than Rs. 3,000 per annum.

Women's Education

Education for women will primarily consist of adult literacy and functional literacy programs. Adult literacy should be made a compulsory activity of the MagalirMandrams and women's welfare branches. The assistance of the department of education involving use of the district education officer and his staff should be sought. The perspective plan has allotted rupees 1.50 cores for adult literacy and this facility should be used in the women's education program. The plan envisaged the functioning of 40,000 centers for functional literacy during the fifth plan.

Programmer for Education

Self-help group have emerged as one of the major strategies in group formation and various schemes of the government of India have shown that strong women groups could contribute substantially to the development and convergence of service and activities. Experience with various programmer and projects have highlighted the benefits of formation of women group for building confidence and focusing on development tasks. Different groups in various states all over the country have focused on skill development and awareness generation, promoting economic development thought income generation activities, inculcating thrifts credit management activities among poor women.

Education and Employment Opportunities for Women

In 1967-68 the number of high schools for girls was 6 government schools, ninety four district board, panchayat union schools, 34 municipal ant 200 and 8 aided schools. The total strength of girls in these school was 5,30,499. Every year about 8,000 secondary grade teachers and 3,6000 higher grade teachers were trained. In 1959 during the congress rule the figures numbered only 3,000. During the D.M.K regime rules (1970-72) there were 5,835 graduates, 27,295 matriculates and 46,052 non-matriculate women teachers. Women's Welfare Branches There were 48 women's welfare branches in the state during the congress rule in Tamil Nadu. The number was raised to 50 during the DMK rule of the one at Pammal, Chingleput district and the other at Aziz agar south Aroct district were meant exclusively for denitrified tribal women. The object of these branches was to educate women in household arts and child by the field staff. Service home for women The second most important social welfare work undertaken by the department was the running of service homes. Theses service homes helped the socially handicapped women including widows and destitute women. The first service home for destitute women was started in 1948 at Tambaram. Two others were started later in

Gandhinagar, along with Kasturba Training school. These homes functioned during DMK rule also. At Tambaram a separate section was run for the physically handicapped women and children with a sanctioned of 30 adults and 20 children. The other State-Aided service homes were run at Kasturba Sevikashram, Trichy, Gandhi Gram, Madurai district, Avvai Ashram, Sivasailam and Anna Anadhai Illam, Organdam. The children were also taken care of in these homes till seven years of age in case of girls and five in case of boys.

Hostels for Working Women

The lower middle income group women who worked for a living away from their homes and parents found it hard to find accommodation. So the government to meet this problem decided to run hostels for working women. They also assisted the voluntary institutions which ran hostels through grants-in-aid scheme of the board. This department founded hostels in 1967 in emote. 2 It sanctioned strength was twenty five and the annual expenditure amounted to Rs.25,000/-. The government also proposed to encourage and support voluntary institutions which would run hostels for working women and they proposed to give grants-in-aid for putting up their own buildings. Women's Voluntary Service in Tamil Nadu

The women's voluntary service of Tamil Nadu

The was permitted to start two Pre-schools one in South Madras and another in North Madras as per- G.O.Ms.NO. 1039, during 1972-73 and they were sanctioned a grant of Rs. 2,000/- for the purpose. The director women's voluntary service, Tamil Nadu, Madras has now represented that they were able to start one pre-school at Sastri Nagar only, that they were able to start one pre-schools at Sastri Nagar only that they were not able to the other pre-school on Madras that now Thiruvalluvar Social Service centre Washermanpet and Royapettah Magalir Mandram are willing to start pre-schools. The director has therefore requested to permit them to utilize the grant of Rs.1000/- for the Sastri Nagar preschool during the period from 1973-74 and also to sanction a grant of Rs.2000/- to start more schools at Royapettah and Washermanpet.

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